
NUTRITIONAL AND SENSORY EVALUATION OF A LOCAL BEAN PUDDING "EKURU" ENRICHED WITH TUBER CROPS

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ABSTRACT

"Ekuru" is a steamed cowpea based gel that is popular in south west, Nigeria. The proximate composition and sensory properties of "Ekuru" produced from cowpea, sweet potato and tigernut were investigated. "Ekuru" was prepared by adding sweet potato and tigernut separately to cowpea at the ratio of 70%;30%. The result of proximate analysis of the ekuru samples revealed no significant difference in the moisture (70.37- 71.22%), ash (0.06-0.07%), crude protein (6.22-7.66%) and dry matter (28.78-29.63%) contents while there is significant difference in fat (2.47-4.43%). Results of the sensory analysis also revealed that there was no significant difference ($p>0.05$) between the 100% cowpea ekuru and the other samples except for texture of the 70; 30% cowpea and tigernut substitution (with value of 6.80, 7.53 and 6.60 respectively). This study therefore suggests that the blend of 30% sweet potato and tigernut with cowpea can be used for the production of ekuru with desirable sensory quality thereby providing an alternative way of utilizing these root crops.

Keywords: Proximate, Sensory, Evaluation, Ekuru, Tuber Crops

INTRODUCTION

'Ekuru' is a cowpea based staple food in Nigeria and in some other West African countries. It is a popular food in Southern and Western part of Nigeria and it serves as a nutritional food in cultural, traditional and religious functions especially among the Yoruba's in South West Nigeria (Jenfa and Akinrinde, 2019). Although it is a steamed cowpea paste product like 'moi-moi', it is different in composition, preparation and it exhibits distinctive rheological properties (Adedokun et al., 2014). The incorporation of air into the paste through whipping during its processing is an important operation which confers the unique fluffiness of the paste and it is considered as an important quality characteristic of the product. 'Ekuru' is served with fried pepper stew and then mashed up with pepper stew, while some people also enjoy the pudding with fermented maize pudding (Agidi or Eko), which is also cereal-based food (Olaleye et al., 2018). Cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata*) seed contributes to a large extent the protein intake of several rural and urban families; hence is said to be the poor man's major source of protein (Ubbor et al., 2022). Previous researchers reported that cowpea is an important source of essential macronutrients and micronutrients (Luthria et al., 2014) such as iron, calcium, phosphorus, potassium, magnesium, sodium, magnesium, sodium, (Okereke and Hans-Anukam, 2015), zinc, manganese, copper, selenium, vitamin A, vitamin C, vitamin B6, thiamin, riboflavin, niacin, pantothenic and folate (Ubbor et al., 2022). The seeds are considerably cheaper than most crops and is said to be a good food security crop as it blends well with other recipes (Ubbor et al., 2022).

Sweet potato (*Ipomoea batata*), is an extremely versatile and nutritious crop that serves as a very good vehicle for addressing some health related problems (Parle and Monika, 2015). It is a source of macro and micronutrients such as carbohydrates, carotenes, thiamine, riboflavin, niacin, potassium, zinc, calcium, iron, and vitamin C (Ubbor et al., 2022). Sweet potato can be consumed in different forms such as boiled, fried or cooked with other staple foods like beans. Despite the potentials of sweet potato, it is highly underutilized (Sanoussi et al., 2016). According to FAOSTAT (2023), Nigeria produced 4.25 million metric tonnes of sweet potato, making it the largest producer in Africa and the 2nd largest globally. Tiger-nut (*Cyperus esculentus*) is a monocotyledonous, edible perennial plant belonging to the grass family *Cyperaceae* (Knazicka et al., 2026). Tiger nuts are tiny, approximately the size of a peanut (Adenowo & Kazeem, 2020), and are either eaten raw or after soaking for a few hours in water. Tiger nuts have a rich **phytochemical** profile that is composed of flavonoids, organic acids, alkaloids, glycosides, (Metsämuuronen & Sirén, 2019), monounsaturated fatty acids, tannins, phytates, and oils. With tiger nut oil having a comparable nutritional profile to olive oil (Codina-Torrella et al., 2015). The nuts also have a significant amount of starch which is an inexpensive and renewable dietary element (Yang et al., 2022). Despite the relatively low protein content, tiger nuts have yet been demonstrated to be effective against diabetes and colon cancer. The fiber content of the nuts also helps alleviate digestive problems and obesity (Ihedioha et al., 2019). Excellent antioxidant qualities of the nuts due to their flavonoid content may be utilized as natural antioxidants against free radicals (Samuel et al., 2023).

'Ekuru' is usually produced using cowpea but for the purpose of this research work, sweet potato and tiger nut were added to cowpea in the production of 'Ekuru'. The production of cowpea and tuber crops pudding will increase their consumption for better nutritional status of all age groups and economical perspective. The nutritional and sensory properties of "Ekuru" from cowpea enriched with sweet potato and tiger nut are yet to be explored. Therefore the objective of this work was to investigate the nutritional properties and organoleptic taste of cowpea based recipe (Ekuru) enriched with sweet potato and tiger nut. The production and evaluation of pudding using cowpea and tuber crops involves blending protein-rich legume flour with starch-rich tuber crops to create a highly nutritious, steamed product. Research indicates that incorporating sweet potato improves the texture and fiber content while maintaining acceptable organoleptic qualities, particularly at low substitution levels, aiding in the fight against protein-energy malnutrition.

METHODOLOGY

Source of samples

Cowpea, sweet potato, tigernut were purchased from old market, Bida, Niger state. Nigeria.

Preparation of diet samples

The samples were prepared according to the method described by Akusu and Klin-Kabari (2012)

Preparation of Ekuru

The method described by Akusu and Klin-Kabari (2012) was modified and used for the preparation of Ekuru. Cowpea seeds were soaked in water to soften the seed coat. They were

manually dehulled and wet milled into a smooth paste using a hammer mill. Salt was added, whipped thoroughly and scooped into a nylon, packaged and steamed for 45 minutes. They were allowed to cool at room temperature before analyses.

Preparation of Ekuru with Cowpea and sweet potato

2kg of Cowpea seeds was sorted to remove dirt. It was then steeped for 30mins to soften the seed coat and the hull was removed. The dehulled cowpea was added 0.6kg of peeled sweet potato. The mixture was wet milled into a smooth paste. Salt was added, whipped thoroughly and scooped into a nylon, packaged and steamed for 45 minutes. They were allowed to cool at room temperature before analyses.

Preparation of Ekuru with Cowpea and tiger nut

2kg of Cowpea seeds and tiger nut were sorted to remove dirt separately. The cowpea was then steeped in water for 30mins to soften the seed coat and the hull was removed. The tiger nut was steeped in water for 8 hours. The dehulled cowpea was added 0.6kg of tiger nut. The mixture was wet milled into a smooth paste. Salt was added, whipped thoroughly and scooped into a nylon, packaged and steamed for 45 minutes. They were allowed to cool at room temperature before analyses.

Chemical Analysis

Proximate analysis: Moisture content, protein, fat, ash and crude fiber was determined by AOAC method (2012). Carbohydrate content was determined by difference.

Sensory Evaluation

The 'Ekuru' samples were subjected to organoleptic analysis using a total of twenty semi-trained panelist drawn from staff

and students of federal polytechnic, Bida, Niger State, for the evaluation. Each of the 'Ekuru' samples were placed in 20 coded clean white plates (30 gram per plate) and served at room temperature ($28 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$) to the panelists in a sensory evaluation booth with fluorescent lights on. The assessors were requested to eat the 'Ekuru' and score each sample using a 9-point Hedonic scale; where 1 = extremely dislike and 9 = extremely like. Attributes evaluated include; appearance, taste, texture, hardness and overall acceptability. Water was provided for rinsing of their mouths in between tests to prevent carry-over of attributes.

Statistical analysis

The Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was performed on the data obtained from all analysis. Duncan Multiple Range Test was utilized in order to determine whether or not there were significant differences between means at 95% confidence level ($p < 0.05$).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

Proximate compositions of the Ekuru samples

Table 1 shows the result of the proximate composition of the prepared Ekuru. Moisture content ranged from 70.24% to 71.22% in the ekuru samples. Ekuru enriched with tiger nut (sample C) had the highest moisture content while ekuru with 100% beans (sample A) were the least. Ash content ranged from 0.06% in (sample C) to 0.07% in both sample A and C. The fat content ranged from 2.47% in sample B to 4.43% in sample C. Protein content was highest in sample A (7.66%) while sample B (6.22%) had the lowest. Crude fibre ranged from 0.17% to 0.18%. Sample A had the highest crude fibre content and

sample B and C had the least (0.17%). The carbohydrate content of the samples ranged from 16.99% to 20.39%. sample B recorded the highest value while sample C had the least value.

Table 1. Proximate composition of the ekuru samples

Samples	Moisture	Ash	Fat	Protein	Crude fibre	CHO	Drymatter	Energy
A	70.37a+0.60	0.07 ^a +0.00	3.94b+0.00	7.66a+0.06	0.18a+0.00	17.78 ^{ab} +0.66	29.63a+0.60	137.26a+2.37
B	70.69a+1.74	0.07a+0.00	2.47c+0.00	6.22a+0.99	0.17b+0.00	20.39a+0.76	29.31a+1.74	128.61a+6.96
C	71.22a+1.30	0.06ba+0.0 0	4.43a+0.00	7.14a+0.06	0.17b+0.00	16.99b+1.36	28.78a+1.30	136.38a+5.23

Values are mean + SD (standard deviation). Mean values with the same letters along a column are not significantly different (p-value<0.05) using Duncan's multiple comparison test

Keys:

Sample A : 100% beans

Sample B: 70% beans; 30% sweet potato

Sample C: 70% beans; 30% tiger nut

Sensory scores of the Ekuru samples

Table 2 shows the mean sensory scores for the ekuru samples. taste ranged from 7.07 for sample C to 7.93 for sample B. Appearance ranged from 7.20 and 7.53 with sample A having the highest value and sample B the least value. Texture ranged from 6.60 to 7.53. sample B had the highest value while sample C had the least value. Hardness of the samples ranged from 7.00 to 7.67. The overall acceptability ranged from 7.13 to 8.67. sample B recorded the highest value and sample C had the least value.

Table 2. sensory attributes of the Ekuru samples

Samples	Taste	Appearance	Texture	Hardness	acceptability
A	7.20a+1.42	7.53a+1.46	6.80ab+1.21	7.67a+1.05	7.93ab+1.33
B	7.93a+1.33	7.20a+1.21	7.53a+0.99	7.27a+1.28	8.67a+0.72
C	7.07a+1.49	7.27a+1.22	6.60b+1.24	7.00a+1.13	7.13b+1.60

Values are mean + SD (standard deviation). Mean values with the same letters along a column are not significantly different (p-value<0.05) using Duncan's multiple comparison test

Keys:

Sample A: 100% beans

Sample B: 70% beans; 30% sweet potato

Sample C: 70% beans; 30% tiger nut

DISCUSSION

The chemical composition of foods are necessary as they act as sources of nutrition to both humans and animals or structural components of large molecules with specific functions as stated in recommended daily allowance (Eke-Ejiofor and Kporna, 2019). Table 4.1 shows the proximate composition of the samples. Moisture content of the samples

ranged from 70.37% to 71.22% with the highest value in sample C (70%cowpea: 30% tiger nut) and sample A (100%cowpea) having the least value. The samples were not significantly different ($p>0.05$) from each other. The moisture content of the present study is higher than value (49.78 to 60.70%) reported by Beleya and Eke-Ejiofor (2020) on epiti wrapped with different leaves. Low moisture content of any food product enhances the storage stability of such food by preventing mould growth (Eke-Ejiofor et al., 2023). This indicates that the samples of the present study may not be stored for a long period but for instant consumption. Ash content is a measure of the total amount of mineral content or inorganic material that remains after burning. The ash content in the present study ranged from 0.06 - 0.07% with sample C (70%cowpea: 30% tiger nut) as the lowest and sample A (100%cowpea) as the highest. The ash content in the present study is lower than the value reported by Eke-Ejiofor et al., (2023) for a Comparative Study on Different Brands of Beans Flour Sold in Selected Markets in Port Harcourt, Nigeria and Their moi-moi (Pudding) Making Potential. Samples A and B were significantly different ($p<0.05$) from sample C. Ash content of any food is an indication of mineral content in such food product. There was significant difference ($p<0.05$) between the samples in fat content. The fat content of the present study is lower than the value of 5.44 to 6.93% and 6.98 to 9.28% reported by Beleya and Eke-Ejiofor (2020) in moi moi and epiti wrapped in different leaves. According to Otunola and Afolayan (2018), the lower fat content of pudding reduce the rate at which rancidity sets in subsequently increasing the shelf life and also makes the products suitable for weight management.

The protein content of the ekuru samples was not significantly different ($p>0.05$) but sample A had the highest score. The protein content obtained from the present study is significantly lower than the 17.60 to 26.90% reported by Otunola and Afolayan (2018) for cowpea and water yam flour moi moi. Protein is essential in the diet for growth, development and survival of human beings. It also works in synergy with minerals to enhance growth, provide energy, repair and regulate body processes (Okwunodulu et al., 2019)

The crude fiber content of the pudding ranged from 0.17%-0.18% with sample A having the highest with no significant ($p>0.05$) difference amongst the samples. The fiber content obtained in this study for ekuru are lower than 0.78% reported by Obueh, et al. (2017) in the study Proximate and microbiological compositions of some foods and vegetable from food vendors at Lagos street in Benin city. Dietary fibers function in the body to slow down the rate of glucose absorption into the blood (Ugwu et al., 2022). Therefore a high intake of fibers is associated with a reduced risk of several chronic diseases, including cardiovascular diseases (CVDs), cancer, type 2 diabetes, and obesity (Ugwu et al., 2022).

Carbohydrate content of the samples was significantly different but sample B (70% cowpea; 30% sweet potato) had the highest value. The carbohydrate value obtained is significantly lower than the value (36.80 to 43.50%) reported by Otunola and Afolayan (2018) for cowpea/water yam flour moi-moi, and the value 29% and 33% reported by Ugwu, et al. (2022) for nutritional analysis of african yam bean and bambara nut pudding. The differences in carbohydrate content could be due to variation in recipes used in the preparation of the ekuru

samples. The high energy contents (128.61 - 137.26%) indicates that it is a good source of energy and can supply most of the body's energy requirement. The result of the sensory scores is presented in Table 3.2. The scores for overall acceptability and appearance varied from 7.27-6.6 and 7.47-6.93 respectively. There was decrease in the scores as tigernut and sweet potato flours were added however the decrease was not significant ($P>0.05$). The result revealed that the texture and taste of the "Ekuru" varied significantly ($P<0.05$)

CONCLUSION

The study has shown that 30% orange fleshed sweet potato and 30% tiger nut could be substituted with cowpea to produce ekuru that would be well accepted by the consumers. The use of tiger nut and sweet potato in ekuru production would promote production, value addition and diversification of utilization of the crops in Nigeria and environs. This would create wealth and enhance food security. However the high moisture content of the samples would affect their keeping quality and shelf life and therefore the need for immediate consumption. Sensory evaluation result showed preference for ekuru produced from sample A (100% cowpea), which may be attributed to familiarity with ekuru from cowpea, although ekuru from sweet potato substitution up to 30% inclusion were acceptable

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